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Abstract

The objective of the present paper is to offer new model of ME teacher with knowledge and qualifications necessary for the demands of the modern world, the specialists with appropriate education and practical training in Maritime field. Our intention is also to offer development of new curriculum for ME teachers' training to make them as well-trained as possible so that they can render knowledge of English and of the subject to their students in the best possible way. It is also our goal to develop a new curriculum for the training of maritime English Professionals, to ensure that they transfer their knowledge of the English language and the relevant industry in the most effective way.

For writing the present paper we have analyzed a lot of articles dedicated to such subject as phenomenon of ESP teacher, we considered the existing types of teachers involved in teaching ESP and ME in particular and on basis of this comparison we offered new model of ME teacher who is supposed to receive type of qualification on basis of offered curriculum containing specific subjects from different disciplines of Maritime field in native and English languages. In order to correlate the successful work of the teacher with the level of preparation of the students as from linguistic as well from professional points of view we have worked out the best possible models that would guarantee maximally successful cooperation between teachers and students for the purpose of receiving the best possible results in the process of studies.

Keywords: maritime English, effective way of teaching, language teachers.

Introduction

The field of ESP is very important part of English language teaching as it guarantees the knowledge of English for professionals of different fields that is essential in the era of globalization. ESP comprises different fields: English for Medicine, English for Engineering, English for Social Sciences, English for Maritime field, etc. The quality of knowledge of English by specialists in their professional scope depends on the quality of teaching they have received that is in its turn dependent on the knowledge and qualifications of teachers responsible for teaching students i.e. on the ESP teachers and ME teachers if considered in the context of Maritime field.

The objective of the present article is to offer model of ESP teacher and ME teacher in particular to meet demands of maritime field in the modern world. For this purpose, we have considered all existing types of teachers who teach English for Specific Purposes in our country and offered the new model for preparation of ESP teachers and also tried to develop sketches of the curriculum according to which the ESP teachers can receive adequate training to be able to teach English to their students on the proper level. We have also discussed the models of ESP students and correlated the models of ESP teachers to ESP students to try to single out the best variants whose cooperation in the teaching/learning process would result in good students' knowledge of English in the professional context. It is worth mentioning that the main aim of the present paper is to consider Maritime English and offer new model of ME lecturers although we consider ME in the ESP context as it belongs to it.

Methodology

For writing the present paper we have analyzed a lot of articles dedicated to such subject as phenomenon

of ESP teacher, we considered the existing types of teachers involved in teaching ESP and ME in particular and on basis of this comparison we offered new model of ME teacher who is supposed to receive type of qualification on basis of offered curriculum containing specific subjects from different disciplines of Maritime field in native and English languages. In order to correlate the successful work of the teacher with the level of preparation of the students as from linguistic as well from professional points of view we have worked out the best possible models that would guarantee maximally successful cooperation between teachers and students for the purpose of receiving the best possible results in the process of studies.

Analysis of Research

ESP is equally important for such basic linguistic activities as teaching and translation although in case of the latter it is more often referred to as specialized English. Such issue as models of ESP teacher implying: 1) EFL teacher with practical experience in ESP, and 2) subject teacher with knowledge of foreign language is actual. In addition to the existing models of ESP teachers, linguists or specialists of specific fields we decided to develop a new model of ESP teacher or ME teacher in particular who after receiving certain qualifications would be able to meet the needs of ESP students at higher education institutions.

The same can be observed in the field of Maritime education. Maritime English is a branch of ESP, officially adopted by IMO as means of communication between seafarers all over the world. Successful knowledge of ME can be guaranteed only if cadets are taught it on the proper level by adequately qualified language specialists. Nowadays ME is taught either by EFL teachers with experience of teaching ME in maritime institutions or by professional seafarers. Captains,

chief officer, after receiving language certificates work as ME teachers thus teaching ME to the students.

As our objective is to consider phenomenon of ESP teacher and offer the new model of ESP teacher and ME teacher in particular we decided to consider this phenomenon in the context of its related issues such as, ESP methodology, ESP text (adapted and authentic), ESP terminology and support our ideas by opinions of different scientists who have been considering this subject during last 30 years. All these issues being part of ESP prepare the reader of the present article to percept the main subject of the paper – new model of ME teacher.

Our objective is to offer a new model of ME teacher implies teacher with education both in linguistic field and maritime subjects as well the experience in maritime field to make them more qualified for ME teaching and guarantee that their lectures are maximally interesting and fertile for future specialists of maritime field.

Nowadays the majority of ESP teachers are ordinary English teachers with experience in certain specific field. The other alternative is subject teacher with knowledge of English but due to legislative norms actual percentage of the occupancy of such specialists in teaching ESP is much lower than of EFL teachers. In my opinion ESP lectures can be delivered by both of the above-mentioned types of teachers. They can interchange each other and that would depend on the topic and material to be rendered or they can just cooperate, supplement each other and thus make the lectures and material as useful and as interesting to students as possible. Our opinion can be supported by extract from the article “Role of Functional Academic Literacy in ESP Teaching”: Collaborative work (Team teaching); Chen (2000) holds that the language teacher should not be expected to possess sophisticated content knowledge, but basic concepts are needed to design an ESP syllabus that backs up the content course. Indeed, language teachers have not been trained to teach content subjects but they could definitely be a competent ESP teacher if they participate in content teaching classes and thus develop the flexibility to undergo disciplinary acculturation. In this regard, the content teacher shares the responsibility not only of providing opportunities for the language teacher to overcome the fear of a lack of content knowledge but also of introducing him/her to the modes of disciplinary thought and values. Therefore, language teachers can ask for assistance from content teachers. When this is the case, it is possible, through collaboration and cooperation, for both language and content teachers to develop the confidence and the competence to effectively integrate language and content instruction in ESP teaching, which entails 1) analysis of texts, materials, and curriculum; 2) classroom observation, reflection, and feedback; 3) collaborative action research and reflection; 4) development of integrated or complementary lessons, materials, or curricula; 5) collaborative or team teaching (Crandall, 1998). [2:402]

On account of teaching ME the similar situation was described by C. Cole, P. Trenkner, B. Pritchard in the article “Profiling the Maritime English Instructor”:

A noteworthy procedure where general English teachers who wish to become qualified Maritime English instructors is applied at the Qingdao Ocean Shipping Mariners College (QMC), P.R. China. The corresponding teacher is supervised by an experienced Maritime English lecturer and has to acquire or upgrade her/his maritime background knowledge by attending specific courses performed at the College. Then s/he has to embark on a vessel, be it a training ship or an active merchant ship, for a contracted period of time, at least three months. After this s/he has to sit an examination designed to assess the general maritime and specific Maritime English knowledge acquired. Having successfully passed all these steps, only then will the employee be entitled to be called a Maritime English lecturer and to teach Maritime English to nautical and/or engineering degree courses, and (sic!) at an increased hourly rate”. (7:4)

In the article “Maritime English Instruction – Ensuring Instructor’s Competence” the same authors offer classification of existing types of ME instructors that in our opinion should be just cited here: “1. Career specialists: These persons are recognised as they are Graduates/Qualified Teachers, have become “marinated” – have seafaring credibility, have a reasonable institutional standing, may (or may not) be “qualified” to teach ME. 2. English language and literature graduates: are lovers of English, are not necessarily interested in applied linguistics, prefer to teach general English, are often asked to teach ME but fail to meet the STCW standards. 3. Former seafarers: are technical experts but not necessarily skilled at English, not necessarily skilled at teaching, often over-challenge their students, could deliver technical subjects in English. (5:128-130)

The model of the teacher we intend to suggest implies the basic knowledge of special maritime subjects by the teacher of English. This kind of teacher will be able to deal with technical phenomena, will be aware of basic terms in all specific maritime fields and being prepared for each lecture will be able to find the meaning of any new term and it will be much more understandable to such specialist than to ordinary EFL teacher. We would like to mention that the idea of writing the present article was inspired by various scientific works, one of them is “ESP in-service teacher training programs” by Peyman R. in which the author mentions: “English major ESP instructors can fulfill course goals much better than specialists in the field provided that they possess a certain level of background knowledge in their students’ academic subjects of ESP teaching in order to meet this challenge. In other words, ESP teachers are supposed to be knowledgeable in content areas as well and be able to elicit knowledge from students. However, language teachers are trained to teach linguistic knowledge rather than a content subject. Hence, they may be insufficiently grounded to teach subject matters (Richards & Rodgers, 2001)”. [10:280]

When it comes to ME in particular it is relevant to bring the words of the above-mentioned scientists. Thus Clive Cole, Peter Trenkner, Boris Pritchard in their articles: “Profiling the Maritime English Instructor”, “Maritime English Instruction – Ensuring Instructor’s Competence”, “The Profile of an Integrated Maritime English Lecturer – Status-quo and Nice-to-have”

address the phenomenon of ME teacher whereas we try to offer the model of education for ME lecturer that would help to meet demands of the field. It is worth noting that these scholars mention the issue in the article "Profiling the Maritime English Instructor" in the following way: "If the majority of institutions were to promote and encourage Maritime English qualifications many of today's problems would be solved and this paper made redundant. However, reality looks quite different. Thus, one of the goals of this initiative is to investigate why this is the case". This would be really necessary as "teachers of Maritime English, just like all other instructors involved in the education and training of seafarers, have to comply with the STCW 1978, as amended, which requires, that "instructors, supervisors and assessors are appropriately qualified for the particular types and levels of training or competence or assessment of seafarers either on board or ashore. (6:154)

Discussion of models of ESP teachers both the existing ones and the newly offered one entails consideration of such issues as design of curriculum for ESP teachers of newly offered model, singling out the models of students according to their knowledge of English and of the subject, discussion of peculiarities of specific texts and analyzing the ways of teaching specific terminology that is the most important part of any specific text and consequently is major task for ESP teacher during the work in the class.

We would like to offer that some Maritime educational centre or institution assumes designing a program i.e. curriculum for Maritime English teacher so that linguistic and specific maritime educations are combined within this program. In our opinion the educational program should be linguistic one containing basic maritime subjects of all maritime disciplines within its curriculum.

ME teacher educated according to new model of education would be successful at teaching ME and also at teaching ME through methodology of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL). Such education will help to render ME more efficiently not only on the level of specific texts containing important information but also on the level of SMCP as the more the teacher visualizes the situation the better he/she can explain it. At present there are no maritime higher education institutions in the world implementing such programs, the only one is mentioned by C. Cole, P. Trenkner and B. Pritchard in their article "Profiling the Maritime English Instructor": "An interesting and attractive qualification system is applied, for instance, at Danish MET institutions. Here deck, engineer or former radio officers possessing an extraordinarily high standard of English and wishing to teach Maritime English have to take a reduced, but more than basic, extramural course of two years following an individually tailored programme which includes methodology, (applied) linguistics, curriculum development etc., at a specified university which is authorised to perform such. All the courses are paid for by the corresponding maritime academy and the time spent is counted as work time". (7:6-7) Our offer is to integrate similar program at some

maritime higher education institution for English language specialists in order to teach them the basics of Maritime field.

The knowledge of the subject by ESP/ME teacher is very important especially when dealing with terminology of certain field. Terminology is studied much better when its essence is familiar to the teacher and the learner. Therefore, the competency of the teacher is that important. In our opinion, it is more efficient to teach terms via bilingual technical dictionaries and English-English explanation could be studied when translation of the term is already familiar to the learner. Different scientists had different opinions on account of teaching technical vocabulary. We would like to mention some of them: "Swales (1985) proposed that the importance of teaching vocabulary in ESP is widely accepted. However, Hutchinson and Waters (1987) believed that the teaching of technical vocabulary is not the responsibility of the ESP teacher. With regard to dealing with unfamiliar technical vocabulary in ESP classes Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998) believe that in many cases there is a one-to-one relationship between the terms in English and the learners' first language, and so it will be enough to translate the term into the learners' native language after a brief explanation". [10:268]

When intermediate or advanced students of English learn to read specific texts and remember its terminology, after the topic is explained by ESP teacher with special qualifications in the field of ESP, they will be able to communicate on the given topic much more easily than if the topic was not familiar to them. In this way the teachers qualifications combined with students' level and motivation can result in good communicative skills that are necessary for any specialist in professional practice and so important for seafarers and maritime field in general.

Hutchinson and Waters mention: "ESP is not different in kind from any other form of language teaching, in that it should be based in the first instance on principles of effective and efficient learning. Though the content of learning may vary there is no reason to suppose that the processes of learning should be any different for the ESP learner than for the General English learner. There is, in other words, no such thing as an ESP methodology, merely methodologies that have been applied in ESP classrooms, but could just as well have been used in the learning of any kind of English. (Hutchinson and Waters 1987, p. 18) [8:3]

Although, Hutchinson and Waters say that methodology of ESP does not differ from GE methodology, we think that as ESP teachers are supposed to teach such subjects as technical and scientific texts, its teaching methodology differs from methodology of GE. Specific scientific and technical texts differ in organization, linguistic parameters, grammatical structures used. Good ESP teachers discuss the organization of text with the students. As it was offered by Bhatia: "Teachers are advised to discuss the organization of texts with the students, to highlight the structure of the texts, and demonstrate the language of qualification in legal writing." [8:12]

As it was noted by Araujo Nunes in the article "Teaching English for Specific Purposes: The GUTs to

do it”: “In the specific case of English for Science and Technology a proper understanding and appropriate use of discourse is the vital factor”. [1:260] Of course EFL teacher can teach discourse better than subject specialist no matter how good his knowledge of English is but the new model of ESP teacher combining knowledge of linguistics with the knowledge of subject would be ideal to deal with the above-mentioned task.

The aim of ESP teaching is to teach students to work with authentic texts i.e. manuals, specific literature, internet resources. ESP teachers work with both adapted and authentic materials. We think that authentic ESP materials should be used in ESP course after certain period of time has passed since the start of ESP course. At the beginning even intermediate and advanced students will find it difficult to deal with authentic specific texts even if they are connected to their specialty and the contents is familiar to them in the native language. One of the objectives of ESP teaching is to enable students to work with Internet resources in this way enriching and keeping up-to-date their professional knowledge. Successful work with authentic texts is the best basis for it.

We think it is quite wise to offer more complicated texts in textbooks than the authentic ones are. In such texts difficult grammar structures are used, the ideas are offered in complicated way. The idea of offering such texts is to teach students to work with maximally difficult texts that are even more difficult than those the students are supposed to work with during their professional lives seems to be realistic and fruitful as it is well-known fact that transition from complicated material to more simple is easier than vice versa.

We think that texts of maritime field can be divided according to registers and would like to refer to our article “Maritime English as part of ESP and as Means of Different Communication Levels” presented at IMLA 20:

“We would like to work out our own classification and divide Maritime English into:

- 1) Maritime English for Academic Purposes (science, teaching) – MEAP
- 2) Maritime English for Professional Purposes – MEPP
- 3) Maritime English for Colloquial Purposes – MECP”(12:)

The documents adopted by IMO and the texts different onshore maritime organizations work with can be allocated to the I type – academic texts. We think that if students are given some extracts from such authentic documents during their studies that would become good basis for them to work with such documents in the future. There are several advantages for such approach: the first one is that working with more difficult text facilitates work with easier text; a lot of seafarers work onshore after they complete their career at sea and if they are prepared to work with documents of academic register their English will be sufficient to work in different maritime organizations where only communication-oriented English is not sufficient and thorough understanding of maritime documents written in complicated English will be required.

Results and Discussion

Prior to transition to the main subject of our work we would like to consider the models of ESP teachers that exist in our country. As it is common in the whole world, generally ESP courses and ME course in particular are taught by English language specialists who acquire the background knowledge of the field they work in. Usually at least two or three years are necessary for language specialist who does not have any specific knowledge to assimilate in the specific field. The other type of ESP teacher is the specialist of the specific field with the knowledge of foreign language but the percentage of occupancy of the former type is much larger than of the latter.

It should be noted here that the above-mentioned is actual generally for our country whereas the situation all over the world can be different. Thus C. Cole, P. Trenkner, B. Pritchard in their article “The Profile of an Integrated Maritime English Lecturer – Status-Quo and Nice-to-have” say: “In the recent years it has become evident that an increasingly large portion of the curriculum in non-native English speaking MET institutions, in some cases 100%, is being taught through English; Piri Reis is a good example of this. The question nonetheless is why should English be the medium of instruction and assessment in preference to that of the local language? And at the core, is this the way ahead?” (6:158) It should be noted that at the above-mentioned University English is taught by professional seafarers who have good command of English and can teach special subjects in English as in the case of Piri Reis University described in the article “The Profile of an Integrated Maritime English Lecturer – Status-Quo and Nice-to-have”.

In the present work we intend to consider existing models of ESP/ME teachers and discuss new model of ESP/ME teacher who in our opinion would receive special qualifications to be able to work in such field as Maritime English and we will also offer the variant of the curriculum that could be applied by some maritime higher education institutions to educate future ME lecturers properly. The main objective for our offer is to ensure improving of ESP studies and ME in particular as when ESP teacher is aware of subject matter i.e. has adequate qualifications provided that ESP students have to be intermediate or advanced students of English, and if they know the subject in their native language, the process of studies will not be too difficult as the only thing students will be obliged to do is to remember English terminology, acquire skills in reading the specific texts that will help them to remember the terms better.

The curriculum for preparation of such model of ESP/ME teacher should include not only linguistic subjects but also fundamentals of special maritime subjects the ESP/ME teacher is supposed to work with in the future. The future ESP/ME teachers should work with already developed ESP courses to acquire as much English terminology of maritime fields as possible. Above all, having gained specific fundamental knowledge in different fields and English terminology of the fields, future ESP/ME teachers should work with samples of authentic texts in order to be able to work with authentic texts used in the maritime field in the future and be qualified to teach them to their students.

Our idea is to offer a kind of unified curriculum for ME teachers all over the world, so that ME teachers are educated according to identical program, consequently they will be able to teach their own students according to the common standards and that will result in good knowledge of English by professionals on the global level. We think that this kind of approach would be solution to ME teachers' education problem in the today's globalized world.

In the present article we are considering phenomenon of ESP teacher and try to offer a new model of ESP teacher on example of ME teacher as Maritime English is part of ESP. Although ESP is much broader concept than ME we would like to draw the reader's attention that in the present article we generally focus on such issue as Maritime English thus using term ESP we still refer to ME.

In our opinion, it is not only qualification of ESP teacher that conditions the result of ESP teaching but also the level of preparation of the students as from linguistic as well from professional points of view.

Intermediate and advanced level of GE combined with knowledge of the subject by the students, facilitates ESP studies process and thus the students' motivation to study ESP course will be raised and consequently the results of the studies will be improved. If this problem is solved then ESP teachers will avoid demotivation of the students of ESP that sometimes has crucial effect on the ESP studies and its results. Here we think it is expedient to refer to the words of Dora Chostelidou in the article "A Record of the Training Needs of ESP Practitioners in Vocational Education":

"Also the problem of demotivation was pointed out. The majority of the respondents claimed that students are poorly motivated; perhaps they feel that the study of the language was imposed up to them by the institutions or they may not appreciate the value of their ESP course.

In addition, the students' lack of interest in learning ESP causes a lot of problems in the teaching process, as most of the participants stated that they cannot develop their students' motivation. ESP teachers declared they need to adapt to the multifaceted nature of ESP and find ways to encourage the students' intention to learn and to act as consultants, which involves diagnosing the learners' language and communicative needs". [4:137]

In the present work we decided to establish the correlation of qualifications and experience of ESP teachers and ESP students that is very important in receiving good results.

I. For this purpose we offer the existing models of ESP teachers:

1. ESP teacher – EFL teacher with the experience in ESP/ME
2. Subject teacher with the knowledge of English
3. ESP teacher holding two degrees both in linguistics and subject area
4. ESP/ME teacher with specific ESP qualifications (newly offered model)

II. And the existing models of potential ESP/ME students:

1. Elementary knowledge of GE (A1, A2)
2. Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2)
3. Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2)
4. Elementary knowledge of GE (A1, A2) with knowledge of specific subject
5. Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2) with knowledge of specific subject
6. Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2) with knowledge of specific subject

In our opinion the most efficient cooperation between ESP teachers and ESP students will be:

1/I ESP teacher – EFL teacher with the experience in ESP – 2,3/II Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2), Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2)

2/I Subject teacher with the knowledge of English –2,3/II Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2), Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2)

4/I ESP teacher with specific ESP qualifications (newly offered model) – 2,3/II Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2), Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2)

The ideal combination of teacher – student cooperation is: 4/I ESP teacher with specific ESP qualifications (newly offered model) – 2,3/II Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2), Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2)

But in reality most often we have to deal with the following combination of ESP teacher-student cooperation model: 1/I ESP teacher – EFL teacher with the experience in ESP/ME - 1,2/II Elementary knowledge of GE (A1, A2), Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2)

The combination 2/I Subject teacher with the knowledge of English (the sample discussed above on the example of Piri Reis University) -3/II Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2) is seldom for Georgia.

In our opinion the 3rd model of ESP teacher - ESP teacher holding two degrees both in linguistics and subject area, in our case it is GE teacher who would be qualified in Maritime field i.e. has fundamental knowledge of general maritime subjects is ideal for teaching ESP/ME but there are not very many ESP/ME teachers with such qualifications in the whole world and if such teacher teaches the model of the student 5,6/II (Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2) with knowledge of specific subject, Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2) with knowledge of specific subject) the best possible results in acquiring ESP for particular field are guaranteed.

The students' models 4,5,6/II (Elementary knowledge of GE (A1, A2) with knowledge of specific subject, Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2) with knowledge of specific subject, Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2) with knowledge of specific subject are very rare in Georgia.

The importance of knowledge of General English by students to take ESP course can be supported by following words of Kaosar M. in the article "The ESP Teacher: Issues, Tasks and Challenges": "Through training, ESP teachers are provided with the necessary knowledge and tools to deal with their own students' specializations. Bojović (2006) reminds that ESP teachers are not specialists in the field, but in teaching English, their subject is English for the profession but

not the profession in English. They help students, who know their subject better than the teachers do, develop the essential skills in understanding, using, and/or presenting authentic information in their profession. A professional ESP teacher must be able to switch from one professional field to another without being obliged to spend months on getting started" [8:18].

In our opinion, the minimum level to acquire ESP is B1 (intermediate), otherwise work with authentic materials would be very difficult even after two years of ESP studies.

In the models of students singled out in this work (4,5,6/II) we mentioned such quality as subject knowledge and the students with such knowledge are ideal for mastering ESP but reality shows that students' models 1,2,3/II - Elementary knowledge of GE (A1, A2), Intermediate knowledge of GE (B1, B2), Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2) are much more common in Georgia and other countries and frequently the issue of simultaneous study of topics in native and English language is very acute. Of course, we fully agree with the idea expressed by Blagojević S. in the article: "Original Texts as Authentic ESP Teaching Material – the Case of Philosophy" when he says that: "In order to enable students of philosophy to understand philosophy texts in English, it is essential that course book texts should comply with the content of other subjects of the curriculum". [3:121] Nevertheless, still we think that if ESP teacher - ESP student combination 4/I (ESP teacher with specific ESP qualifications (newly offered model) - 3/II (Advanced knowledge of GE (C1, C2)) is applied, the cooperation and result could be successful even if the texts in English are rendered earlier than texts on the same topic in the native language.

There are many reasons why we think that it is necessary to give specific qualifications to ESP/ME teachers. We are sure if ESP/ME teacher receives appropriate qualifications before starting the work i.e. is educated according to the model of the curriculum offered in the present article and not during working process when gaining the practica experience as it usually happens, such teacher will be able to render content information more professionally to the students than EFL teachers. In this way ME lecturers would receive adequate qualifications to perform their duties in maximally effective way. We think it is expedient to support this idea by the words of John Swales: "All researches interested in assessing the progress of ESP as a component of ELT agree that one of the most constraining factors to this progress is the lack of "specialized teacher-training" (Swales1985: 214) [9:450]

Conclusion

If the model of Maritime teacher developed in the present article is applied in practice and some Maritime University offers Master's Degree program for EFL teachers to be qualified as ME teachers it could become the serious step in improving the quality of ME teacher training courses in the future. This opinion can be supported by the fact that thorough understanding of the essence of the courses delivered by teachers themselves, the knowledge of terminology on professional level will change the quality of the lectures delivered

and will help students to raise motivation during ESP studies that will result in the improved knowledge of English by professionals of different fields.

In order to implement this idea, the curriculum should be worked thoroughly on basis of collaboration between specialists of linguistics and Maritime field who are supposed to offer fundamentals of their disciplines for ME teachers' curriculum in the scope necessary to receive basic knowledge about the subjects and terminology in English to be able to work with similar authentic materials in English with ME students in future. If such curriculum is worked out, it can become unified basis for producing Maritime English specialists for different maritime educational institutions all over the world that will help in establishing one common standard for ME teacher training.

Abbreviations

GE –	General English
EFL –	English as a Foreign Language
ESP –	English for Specific Purposes
ME-	Maritime English

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